

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B268
 Date: 21 February 2007
 Take Off: 10:48:19
 Landing: 16:27:15
 Flight Time: 5h38m56

Campaign: GFDEX - Reverse Tip Jet

Operating Area: Greenland Coast

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Dawn Quinn	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Ian Renfrew	UEA
5	Flight Manager	Alan Woolley	FAAM
6	Cloud Physics / CCM2	Kate Turnbull	FAAM
7	Core Chem	Mo Smith	FAAM
8	Mission Scientist 2	Nina Peterson	UEA
9	AVAPS	Stuart Heath	FAAM
10	Mission Scientist 3	Carling Hay	University of Toronto
11	Mission Scientist 4	Tadayasu Ohigashi	University of Toronto
12	Mission Scientist 5	Kent Moore	University of Toronto
13	Mission Scientist 6	Steve Outten	Leeds University
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FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B268
 Date: 21/2/07
 Project: GFDEX
 Location: Iceland/Greenland

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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102647		engine start	0.44 kft	000	
103739		engine start again!	0.44 kft	048	
103957		power change	0.45 kft	048	
104819		T/O	0.42 kft	089	from Keflavik
105505		jw/nevz	13.5 kft	269	zero
122039		Sonde 1	18.0 kft	248	
122442		Sonde 2	18.0 kft	270	
122811		Sonde 3	18.0 kft	269	
123149		Sonde 4	18.0 kft	269	
124433		Sonde 5	18.0 kft	118	
125013		Sonde 6	18.0 kft	186	
125442		Sonde 7	18.0 kft	188	
125852		Sonde 8	18.0 kft	187	
131209		Sonde 9	18.0 kft	111	
131748		Sonde 10	18.0 kft	114	
132349		Sonde 11	18.0 kft	114	
132859		Sonde 12	18.0 kft	113	
133618	134615	Profile 1	6.6 kft	069	
133737		Profile 1			interrupt
133904		Profile 1			resume
134615	144601	Run 1	0.00 kft		
141732	142405	Profile 2	0.00 kft		
162715		Land	0.43 kft	088	Keflavik
163951		standstill	0.50 kft	280	63'58.43N, 22'35.76W

B268 Track 21-FEB-07

GFDex Sortie Brief – 21st February 2007 – Reverse Tip Jet (Flight plan 13)

Mission Scientist 1 – Ian Renfrew

Mission Scientists -

Aims

- Map out 3D structure of reverse tip jet using high-level and low-level legs
- Map out near-surface winds and associated air-sea turbulent fluxes
- High-level legs between 15-25 kft, straight and level, generally perpendicular to jet axis
- Dropsonde sampling every 20-25 nm (30-40 km)

GFD13	Time	Manoeuvre	Distance (nm)	Duration (min)	Total time (min)
1	10.30	Take off Keflavík, transit to 62N, 40W	490	~100	~100
2		Straight level run at 20-25 kft, from 62N, 40W to 62N, 42W, perpendicular to jet axis. Science speed. Dropsondes every 20 nm (4 in total).	56	~15	115
3		Straight level run at 20-25 kft From 62N 42W to 61.5N, 41W.	41	~12	127
4		Straight level run at 20-25 kft, from 61.5N, 41W to 60.2N, 41.5W. Science speed Dropsondes every 25 nm (4 in total)	80	~25	152
5		Straight level run at 20-25 kft, from 60.2N, 41.5W to 60N, 43W	46	~13	165
6		Straight level run at 20-25 kft, from 60N, 43W to 59.5N, 41W, perpendicular to jet axis. Science speed. Dropsondes every 20 nm (4 in total).	67	~23	188
7		Rapid descent to ~10,000 ft, profile descent to minimum safe altitude		~10	198
8		Straight low-level leg at MSA, from 59.5N, 41W towards coast, parallel to dropsonde leg (heading ~300deg). If poor visibility ~59.7N,42W	33	~10	208
9		Straight low-level leg at MSA north at 42W to 62.2N, 42W	30	~10	218
10		Straight low-level leg at MSA parallel to leg 8 (~heading 120).	32	~10	228
11		Climb and transit to Keflavik	~570	~120	348

Mission Scientists Debriefing Sheet

Flight No. B268 – Reverse Tip Jet SE of Cape Farewell, Greenland

Date: 21 February 2007

Aims

- Map out 3D structure of reverse tip jet using high-level and low-level legs
- Map out near-surface winds and associated air-sea turbulent fluxes
- High-level legs between 15-25 kft, straight and level, generally perpendicular to jet axis
- Dropsonde sampling every 20-25 nm (30-40 km)

Assessment of the Flight

A highly successful flight.

The high-level dropsonde legs mapped out the low-level tip jet quite well. Unfortunately sonde number 3 failed, leaving only 3 (from 4) sondes in the first cross-section. The downwind 4 sondes were fine. But the sonde 12 from the second cross-section also failed. Fortunately the decent profile partly made up for this failure. The turbulence probe worked well, despite the descent through cloud, fortunately air temperatures were relatively warm.

The low-level 100-ft legs were “moderately turbulent”, low-level wind speeds were up to 40 m/s. Seas were large: wave heights estimated to be 20-30 ft, with a considerable swell orientated approx. downwind. The flight level data showed the jet structure well. Due to low cloud base, Greenland was not visible which limited the low-level legs to 42W due to flight restrictions. The low-level legs across the jet were fairly turbulent, while the leg into the jet felt like something of a roller coaster ride. The turbulence caused some discomfort to a number of mission scientists!

A profile ascent was made to 7500 ft at the end of the low-level sections.

Summary of weather conditions

Zonal flow associated with area of low pressure to south of Greenland. Cloudy at both mid and low-levels. Low-level air temperatures above zero. Precipitation in the area of the tip jet.

Ian Renfrew

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B.268** Date **21 Feb 07** Name **Ian Renfrew** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10.48					Take off
11.14	1			64° 64° 27° 260	Flossi Wqspoint
12.17	1	18,000 ft	345	63° 6' 0", 39° 20'	This Cirrus cloud (entered)
12.20	2	18k ft	373	62° 40° 00'	Drop 1 - in thin cloud. → 12.29 (ocean)
12.24	2	18k ft	370	62° 40°	Drop 2 - in ocean, 12.32
12.28	2	18k ft	369	62 41° 18'	(Drop 3 - failed)
12.31	2	18k ft	269		Drop 4 - in ocean 12.40
12.38	2			(41) Drop	1 st Jet Core 25 m/s @ 900 mb - 1000 mb
				(44)	Drop 2 - Jet 29 m/s @ 900 - 1000 mb
				(52) 14	Drop 4 - Jet 35 m/s at 930 mb
13.44	3 14	18k ft.		61.5 40.9	Drops released
12.50	4	18k ft.		61.2 41.1	Drop 6 ⁽¹³⁾ released (jet ~ 30 m/s at 900-800)
12.53	4	18k ft		60° 54' 0" 41.2	Out of cloud
12.54	4	18k ft.		60° 54' 0" 41.2	Drop 7 ⁽¹⁴⁾ winds late) Drop Dewar Jet 850
12.58	4	18k ft			Drop 8 ⁽⁰³⁾ - in ocean 1.07 (Depth - 750 mb)
12.58					
13.12	5	18k ft.			Drop 9 - in ocean 13.19 (49 m/s jet at 930)
13.17	6	18k ft.			Drop 10 - in ocean 13.25 (44 m/s to 750)
13.21	6	18k ft			Drop 11 - in ocean 39 m/s at 850 - 950
13.29	6	18k ft.			Drop 12 - failed end.
13.29	7	18k ft			Descent starts
13.36	7	7500			Profile descent
13.37	7	6000			Turn & profile descent.
13.38	7	6000			Profile continued

Mission Scientist's Log

Flight No **B268** Date **21.03.07** Name **GNP** Page **1** of **2**

GMT	Run / Profile	Height	Hdg	GPS Position	Remarks (clouds, weather, visibility, winds, sea state etc.)
10.48					Take off.
11.00					wind error.
12.11				62.18 38.18	clouds thickening up more high clouds.
12.15-12.16					Into clouds w/ high water content.
12.21					dropsade 1 T _w -26°C
12.25					" 2
					In clouds from 12.15
12.28					DS3 FAILED.
12.32					DS4 Leg 2
12.4430					DS5
12.50					DS6
12.55					DS7
12.59					DS8 Jet. 700 hPa Leg 4
13.12					DS9 looking good Leg 6 4 m/s 600 hPa
13.18					DS10 - " - 600 hPa.
13.22					DS11 OK.
13.24					DS12 OK Bad?
13.38					Profile wind speed 29 m/s.
13.42		4000ft			35 m/s
13.45	100	50			27 m/s
					Est. wave height 3-6
13.53					~30 m/s
14.00					U2W staying

CLOUD PHYSICS LOG B268

Flight No. B268

Date: 21/02/07

Operator: KFT

Page 1 of 2

G.M.T. DRS Time	PCASP		FSSP	SID1	2D2-C			2D2-P			Remarks
	Conc/cc	Mean R	Block Transfer	Particle Count	Conc/L	Max Size	Habit	Conc/m3	Max Size	Habit	
											PCASP Vref 8V
11:06											2DP rearmed 1Hz
12:10							8				First 2DC picture
12:20:00	48	0.06	30	0	8.5	180	8	2293	200	8	Sonde drop 1, SID restarted
12:22:00	48	0.15	33	0	8.5	650	8	6308	400	8,3	2DP rearmed auto
12:24:44	33	0.06	36	0	8.5	800	8,3,5,4	5000	800	8	Sonde 2 launched
12:28:12	61	0.06	46	0	78	700	8,3	23000	800	8	Sonde 3 launched
12:31:50	108	0.06	56	0	20	525	8,4,	8933	800	8	Sonde 4 launched
12:42:00	97	0.07	72	0	10	200	8,5,4	18388	200	8	Some NOISE on 2DP
12:44:35	49	0.06	77	0	515	525	8	8091	500	8	Some NOISE On 2DP Sonde 5
12:47:00	27	0.14	84	0	17	800	8,4	1866	800	8	
12:50:13	51	0.15	172	0	10.5	800	8	4333	800	8	Sonde 6 launched
12:53:00	89	0.07	223	0	0	0					NOISE on 2DP
12:54:43	96	0.06	223	0	0	0		0	0		NOISE on 2DP Sonde 7
12:58:53	125	0.06	223	0	0	0		0	0		NOISE on 2DP Sonde 8
											SID1 PC and probe restarted
13:12:11	88	0.06	223	0	0	0		0	0		Sonde 9
13:17:50	150	0.06	223	0	0	0		0	0		Sonde 10
13:23:50	131	0.06	224	0	0	0	0	0	0		Sonde 11
13:29:08	103	0.06	224	0	0	0	0	0	0		Sonde 12
13:33:00	206	0.06	224	0	0	0	0	0	0		FL130
13:33:22	166	0.06	224	0	0	0	0	0	0		FL120
13:34:09	169	0.06	224	0							FL110
13:34:48	351	0.12	231	0	400	275	11	24000	3200	8	FL100
13:35:30	274	0.07	248	0	46.5	200	9,8,1	10250	200		FL090
13:37:20	1352	0.12	254	0	236	400	1 (<0C)	4858	400		FL070
13:39:49	260	0.08	280	0	40.5	725	1 (<0C)	241	800		FL060
13:42:00	1028	0.18	338	0	253	225	1 (<0C)				FL040 NOISE on 2DP
13:43:11	776	0.13	468	0	123	275	1, 8				FL030 NOISE on 2DP
13:44:10	602	0.10	546	0	59/5	225	1				FL020 NOISE on 2DP
13:45:23	414	0.10	585	0	12.5	350	1				
14:00:00	706	0.10	675	0	32	650	2,1	725	6400	2	50FT ASL
14:17:32	678	0.08	752	0	18	600	1	3241	2000	2	Start profile climb
14:19:15	568	0.14	817	0	75	800	5,4,9,	9225		5	FL020

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B268 **T/O:** 10:48:19
Date of flight: 21/02/07 **Land:** 16:27:15

A) FFSSP PROCESSING		To Exeter
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer *.txt files from DVD to processing PC Bnnn_FFSSP_hh.txt for each hour of data Bnnn_FFSSP_HVMS.txt		hh = Last sec processed =
2) FTP the files (ascii) from the PC to directory PMSDATA: on FLOODS		File size =
3) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_EXTRACT_TAS a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Path name: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX c) Output directory: PMSDATA: d) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (see comment box)</i> e) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>		Use time just before/after take-off/landing. If T/O /landing just after/before the hour, ensure start/end time is before/after the hour if there is an FFSSP_hh.txt file for that hour.
4) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP]FFSSP_PROCESS_TXT a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) TAS in processing: Y d) Vel threshold (clicks) 0 e) Calibration file: <i>Use the most recent calibration file.</i> Format FFSSP_CALddmmyyyy.txt Calibration files to be stored in MRFB:[PMS.FAST_FSSP] f) Adjust FFSSP time Y/N g) If Y, enter value to add to data time (seconds)		Total glitches = Sec file written ok? Note calibration file used Yes only if gross errors occur in FFSSP time eg; ~ 1hour
5) FLOODS> WAVE a) WAVE> write_procffssp_to_m5,'pmsdata:Bnnn_procffssp.dat', 'mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX','pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp',/auto b) WAVE> exit		Use PVWAVE for this section Note time correction applied to FFSSP by /auto =
6) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procffssp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY (y=x+1) d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>		Input file size = M5 output file size =
7) CHECKS: i). Are FFSSP and JW/Nevzorov LWC synchronized in time? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>JW LWC para 535</i> <i>Nevzorov LWC para 602</i> <i>FFSSP LWC para 1202</i> ii). If not, repeat from step 5b replacing /auto with addt=x which adds x+20 secs to FFSSP time.		Synchronized?

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B268
Date of Flight: 21/02/07

B) 2D PROCESSING		REPROCESS +1hr
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Transfer Bnnn.dat file from CD/DVD to PC	Y	To Compaq
2) Zip up file on PC (Bnnn.zip)	Y	
3) FTP the zipped file (binary) from the PC to the directory SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA] on FLOODS	Y	30034 blocks
4) Log on to FLOODS		
5) Unzip SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.zip	Y	Size of Bnnn.dat = 244911
6) FLOODS> WAVE WAVE> CONVERT_SEADAS_FILE a) Input file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn.dat b) Output file: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section Blocks read = 47673 Blocks written = 47672 Bad reads = 1
7) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SEADAS]READM200_FILE a) Default directory: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Disk file name: SEADAS_DATA:[SEADAS_DATA]Bnnn_seadas.dat d) Comment string: e) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 5 min)</i> f) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land + 5 min)</i> g) Read 2DC: Y h) Read 2DP: Y i) Secondary data: Y j) FSP-SYNC: Y k) cmd.str: Y l) Auto time correction: N m) Full length secondary: N		Start = 120000 End = 150000 Ignore error message scroll (vestigial error from tapes) Are FRW, FSP, IMB, PCA,SEC files in PMSDATA? Y Are they non-zero in size? Y
8) FLOODS> WAVE i). WAVE> imagedisplay a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) File generation no: 0 d) Time from IWC plot: N e) Select probe: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP f) Start time: <i>As in 7e above</i> g) End time: <i>As in 7f above</i> h) Time interval (sec): 5 recommended (0 for all images) ii). WAVE> auto_image a) 2D directory name: PMSDATA: b) Flight number: Bnnn c) Enter date: YYYYMMDD d) Enter start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O – 1 min)</i> e) Enter end time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 1 min)</i> f) Enter time interval (sec) between successive imaged blocks: 10 iii). WAVE> exit to create files iv). FTP ascii *.PS files from PMSDATA: to PC v). Load each into Ghostview or other pdf-converter vi). Output as pdf file (720 dpi resolution), appending name prefix of CORE-CLOUD-PHY_ to converted files	Y	2D image display and printing Must be done from FLOODS itself. Note any problems with images Prepare imagery for Core data From own PC again Start = 120000 End = 144500 54 pp 2DC, 107PP 2DP FAAM_YYYYMMDD_R0_ Bnnn_2Dx-images.ps Notes on this in instructions

<p>9) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.SPEC2D.AUTO]PROCESS2D_AUTO</p> <p>a) Flight number: Bnnn b) Directory: PMSDATA: c) File generation: <i>Hit enter</i> d) Time correction: <i>Time offset of the 2D data</i> e) TAS: Y f) MFD directory: MFDDATA:Bnnn_MFDX g) Probe number: (1) 2DC (2) 2DP (0) Both <i>0 unless either probe known to be faulty</i> h) Start time: <i>0 if unknown (T/O + 30sec)</i> i) End time: <i>240000 if unknown (Land – 30sec)</i> j) Nominal averaging: 0.2 seconds for conversion to M5 k) Particle type 2DC: 8 if known to be in ice cloud 11 if known to be in water cloud l) Particle type 2DP: 8 if known to be in mixed-phase 8 if unknown m) Coefficient choice: 2 n) Output root filename: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROC2D</p>		<p>NB. an error message may appear, floating point exception, rerun and use time quoted in error message, repeat until successful.</p> <p>X = A</p> <p>Start = 120000 End = 150000</p> <p>Time data processed to = 143358 2dproc files present? Y *.2dc, *.2dp and *.dat</p>
<p>10) FLOODS> WAVE</p> <p>i) WAVE> WRITE_PROC2D_TO_M5, 'PMSDATA:BNNN_PROC2D.DAT', 'PMSDATA:BNNN_M5PROC2D' ii). exit</p>		<p>Use PVWAVE for this section</p> <p>Error message about HDDR file should be ignored.</p> <p>Records = 11514, 178</p>
<p>11) FLOODS> MODIFY</p> <p>a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5proc2D b) Datset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: leave blank to use default</p>		<p>X = A Y = (X+1) = B</p>
<p>12) CHECKS:</p> <p>Are 2DC/2DP IWC of comparable magnitude and well-correlated with Nevzorov TWC? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Nevzerov TWC para 605</i> <i>2DC IWC para 1302</i> <i>2DP IWC para 1312</i></p>		<p>Correlated? Y</p>

CLOUD PHYSICS PROCESSING LOG

Flight number: B268
Date of Flight: 21/02/07

C) PCASP PROCESSING		
Processing Stage	Done?	Comments
1) Complete stage 7) in 2D processing Ensures Bnnn_FSP.DAT containing raw PCASP data is written to directory PMSDATA:	Y	
2) FLOODS> RUN MRFB:[PMS.PCASP]PROCPCASP_NEW a) Flight number: Bnnn b) File name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_FSP.DAT c) Root output name: PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP Produces PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.DAT (binary) PMSDATA:Bnnn_PROCPCASP.OUT (ascii) d) Minimum size channel: <i>default = 1</i> <i>If smallest size channel are known to be noisy the value of the highest noise free channel to be entered here</i> e) Calibration volume flow rate: <i>Use the most recent value. 1.8ccs⁻¹</i> <i>Calibration files to be stored in Exeter</i> <i>Entering zero gives default value = 1.0 cm³s⁻¹</i> f) Time correction: <i>Same value as used in 2D processing stage 9d</i> g) Start time: <i>0 if unknown</i> h) End time: <i>240000 if unknown</i>	Y	Min size = 1 Vol flow rate = 1.15 120000 150000
3) FLOODS> WAVE i).WAVE> write_procpcasp_to_m5, 'pmsdata:Bnnn_procpcasp.dat', 'pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp' ii). WAVE> exit	Y	Use PVWAVE for this section
4) FLOODS> MODIFY a) Modifying datasets: pmsdata:Bnnn_m5procpcasp b) Dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdX c) New dataset: mfddata:Bnnn_mfdY d) Parameter description file: <i>leave blank to use default</i>	Y	X = B Y = X+1 = C
5) CHECKS Are PCASP and JW peaks synchronous? <i>In flight_plot, parameters</i> <i>Neph – total blue scatter.</i> <i>PCASP conc para 1550</i>	Y	Merged OK?

FAAM Dropsonde Flight Log

Flight No.	B268	Date	21/02/2007
Page No.	1 of	Operator	SWH

GMT	Sonde No.	Event	Comments
		<i>e.g. launch, splashdown</i>	<i>e.g. wind data? PTH data? Lat/Long NB strings of dropsonde data contain: time, pressure hPa, T deg C, RH %, wind direction deg, wind speed m/s, longitude, latitude, height m</i>
122042	1	Launch	505.40 -26.00 114.51 88.10 9.70 -14.90 -40.011800 62.000700 5494.70 0
122735	1	Land	1005.69 2.50 87.02 26.18 24.37 - 11.37 -40.128450 61.952482 238.98 7
122445	2	Launch	505.30 -26.80 122.09 94.70 10.40 -12.50 -40.735500 62.004100 5496.50 0
123149	2	Land	1007.39 1.70 95.71 18.20 21.62 - 11.07 -40.845530 61.950311 241.46 7
123203.0	3	Launch	505.40 -27.60 93.72 95.00 13.60 -15.30 -42.043000 61.999100 5494.40 0
	3	Land	NO DATA
123151	4	Launch	505.20 -28.10 97.25 82.50 12.80 -15.00 -42.008800 61.999500 5497.40 0
123848	4	Land	1008.35 -0.70 81.07 8.90 21.67 - 9.02 -42.103706 61.941138 281.09 7
	5	Launch	NO DATA
	5	Land	NO DATA
125015	6	Launch	505.10 -25.90 121.89 103.70 16.30 -14.20 -41.188500 61.142700 5499.10 0
125731	6	Land	1004.60 2.32 93.74 16.65 23.85 - 10.27 -41.319074 61.081062 248.77 6
125445	7	Launch	505.20 -24.30 108.36 100.60 17.50 -13.80 -41.348200 60.812400 5497.40 0
130215	7	Land	1003.08 2.77 93.06 12.58 22.80 - 10.20 -41.484536 60.749111 249.72 8
125903	8	Launch	505.30 -23.70 86.63 93.40 15.50 -13.60 -41.507600 60.484800 5496.20 0
130543	8	Land	1000.33 2.89 90.89 18.64 25.98 - 11.48 -41.642528 60.435486 99999.00 7
131218	9	Launch	505.10 -22.80 56.39 105.30 12.90 -14.30 -42.995300 59.972200 5498.60 0
131919	9	Land	1000.27 -0.22 85.30 43.12 1.58 - 0.32 -43.170496 59.902337 270.93 7
131751	10	Launch	505.40 -21.00 34.52 111.00 16.60 -14.70 -42.286700 59.826100 5494.90 0
132436	10	Land	997.34 0.20 94.06 15.05 35.09 -11.89 -42.454322 59.760773 99999.00 6
132406	11	Launch	505.10 -22.80 55.34 94.00 19.10 -14.30 -41.585700 59.651100 5499.80 0
133029	11	Land	995.45 3.81 88.12 28.79 28.29 -12.11 -41.774032 59.600883 99999.00 6
	12	Launch	NO DATA
	12	Land	

Flight:

B268

KEY

- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated
- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevezorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 15/03/2007
12:10:42

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:

DLUs:

- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

Lower:

- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:

Upper:

- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:

- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:

- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:

Aerosol

- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:

Misc Non-Core

- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

22/02/2007 18:25:35

Faults / Incidents Log

Flight No. B268

Date: 21 Feb 2007

Instruments

1. INU – Stopped communicating on change to Navigate at engine start! Engines were shut down and INU communication restored
2. Heimann data invalid – bad flight manager. Was distracted by having to grip seat over turbulent ocean.
3. Ozone data bad – inlet not connected following zero cal.
4. SID1 – no data. Probe/pc not communicating.
5. Two sondes failed on launch.

Aircraft

- 1.

Satcom-H Calls

Nil

Post Flight - Turb Probe Water Traps

1. Indicate Amount of Water: a) Nil b) 1-2 drops c) ¼ full or more d) Ice present
2. Emptied by:
3. Dried by:

Pre-Flighter's Log

Date: 21/2/07

Flight No: B268

Pre-Flighter: BW

Item	✓ or x	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
1	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Hangar	Collect Dustbin, put on a/c	
<u>Aircraft Cabin</u>				
2	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Gases x 3 ON	
3	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cabin	All Racks Checked	
4	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Fwd CorCon	All reqd CBs made	
5	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Aft CorCon	CBs made, PCs ON	
6	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Optical Disk loaded	
7	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	Recording data	
8	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	DLU Status Checked	
9	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	HORACE	HORACE Status Checked	
10	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Satcom H	Power LED ON	
11	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Nevzorov	Checked and OFF	
12	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	GPS	Checked	
13	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	INU	Align	
14	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Cameras Pictures	Checked x 4 OK	
15	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	Instruments Checked OK	
16	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Core Chemistry	CO Flows Checked OK	PKS Cal Gas 5 bar
17	<input type="checkbox"/>	FWVS	Set up	NOT ACTED
18	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Video x 2	Records okay, Rewind	
19	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Delced Rosemount	Heater Checked / Set	
20	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Heimann	Calibration Checked	
21	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	TWC	ON & Checked	
22	<input type="checkbox"/>	GE	Balance checked	
23	<input type="checkbox"/>	INU	Navigate then back to Align	
24	<input type="checkbox"/>	Hubs x 4	Checked ON	
25	<input type="checkbox"/>	Fwd Console	Miss. Sci Laptop CB made	& CB on Port Fwd SSP
26	<input type="checkbox"/>	CNC	Butanol filled	
27	<input type="checkbox"/>	CGPS	Set up	
28	<input type="checkbox"/>	Miss. Sci Laptop	Checked Onboard	
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
	<input type="checkbox"/>			
External Checks overleaf				→

Pre-Flighter's Log

<u>Item</u> <input type="checkbox"/> or <input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	<u>Location</u>	<u>Action</u>	<u>Comments</u>
<u>External</u>			
29	<input type="checkbox"/> Turb Probe	Clean if reqd, Photo taken	
30	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> JW	Cleaned & Checked	
31	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> DI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
32	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> NDI Rosemount	Cleaned & Checked	
33	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Nevzorov	Cleaned/windings checked	
34	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> GE	Cleaned & Checked	
35	<input type="checkbox"/> Lower BBRs	Domes cleaned/checked	
36	<input checked="" type="checkbox"/> Camera Windows	Cleaned	<i>DFC stud on inside of windows</i>
37	<input type="checkbox"/> Heimann	Lens checked OK	
38	<input type="checkbox"/> TWC Cover	Fitted if required	
39	<input type="checkbox"/> All other covers	Removed	
40	<input type="checkbox"/> Dustbin	Returned to hangar	
41	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Check ALL in Toolkit	
42	<input type="checkbox"/> Tools	Avalon informed	
<u>Avalon Checks</u>			Signed
43	<input type="checkbox"/> Upper BBRs Checked & Cleaned		
44	<input type="checkbox"/> ICEX applied		
45	<input type="checkbox"/> Traps empty (weekly only)		

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B268:

Log	Reason
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	20 Mar 2007	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

2 x Forward Facing Cameras
2 x Rearward Facing Cameras

Digital8 video recordings from this flight reside with :

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Daily weather summary 21 February 2007

<p>Large scale situation today:</p>	<p>A large scale barotropic cyclone, with two cyclone centres at the moment, is located over the North Atlantic roughly at 20-50W and 45-55N. It's moving eastward and filling. Aloft the flow is dominated by the same low pressure system. North of Norway there is a 1042 hPa high pressure system. A mesoscale cyclone, possibly a polar low, located at 63N 0W.</p>
<p>Features of interest:</p>	<p>There are strong winds over the Irminger Sea, 30-40kt from the northeast at 10 meters accelerating at Cape Farewell. The 10-m wind speed in a reverse tip jet forecasted to be 50-55kt at 12Z. There is also a clear flow distortion around Iceland.</p>
<p>Action:</p>	<p>A reverse tip jet flight is planned.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 24-48 hours:</p>	<p>The large scale cyclone moves eastward, the centres merging to one centre located south of Iceland after 48 hours at about 56N. The mesoscale cyclone moves northward, deepening by 8 hPa in 36 hours. The high pressure system moves in over Scandinavia but leaving a high pressure ridge at both low and high levels.</p> <p>The winds over the ocean between Iceland and Greenland stay of similar strength and direction but there is not a detectable acceleration at Cape Farewell.</p>
<p>Outlook for the next 48-96 hours:</p>	<p>The same features are dominating the flow but the high pressure system moves farther south having less impact on the flow. The large scale cyclone reaches western Scotland in the 96h forecast. The mesoscale cyclone starts to move eastward, possibly coming into our flight range. It is forecast to deepen in the process, the centre pressure being 993 hPa in the 96h forecast.</p>

Drop Points 21 February 2007

GFDex 21st February Weather Brief

Reverse Tip Jet Flight plan 13

Reverse Tip Jet - GFDex Plan 13

- outbound
- high-level
- low-level
- return
- dropsondes

level -1 Low Cloud for T+12 DT 200702210000 VT 200702211200 ukmo nae main NWP
level -1 Medium Cloud for T+12 DT 200702210000 VT 200702211200 ukmo nae main NWP
MSLP for T+12 DT 200702210000 VT 200702211200 ukmo nae main NWP

level -1 10m Wind for T+12 DT 200702210000 VT 200702211200 ukmo nae main NWP

level -1 10m Wind for T+15 DT 200702210000 VT 200702211500 ukmo nae main NWP

HIRLAM-T: Cloud cover: **Low**, **mid** and **high** clouds.

IT: Wed. 21. Feb. 2007 00Z

VT: **Wed. 21.02.2007 12Z** (+12 h)

HIRLAM-T: Wind in 925hPa.
IT: Wed. 21. Feb. 2007 00Z
VT: **Wed. 21.02.2007 12Z (+12 h)**

HIRLAM-T: Sensible (colored) and latent (contours) heat flux at the surface.

IT: Wed, 21. Feb. 2007 00Z

VT: **Wed. 21.02.2007 12Z** (+12 h)

HIRLAM-T: 3h precipitation, 10m wind and 2m temperature.

IT: Wed. 21. Feb. 2007 00Z

VT: **Wed. 21.02.2007 12Z (+12 h)**

MSLP for T+24 DT 200702210000 VT 200702220000 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+24 DT 200702210000 VT 200702220000 ukmo nae main NWP

MSLP for T+36 DT 200702210000 VT 20070221200 ukmo nae main NWP
level 500 Geopotential Height for T+36 DT 200702210000 VT 20070221200 ukmo nae main NWP

level 925 Wind for T+36 DT 200702210000 VT 200702221200 ukmo nae main NWP

HIRLAM-T: Wind and temperature in 850hPa.

IT: Wed. 21. Feb. 2007 00Z

VT: Thu. 22.02.2007 12Z (+36 h)

Line 1, 21 February 2007

Line 2, 21 February 2007

Line3, 21 Feb. 2007

